

panicle initiation; P and K were applied basally.

Rice plants were inoculated at panicle initiation to booting stage by placing 21-d-old culture of fungus grown in rice straw between the tillers of each hill at water level.

Fungicides were sprayed 7 d after

inoculation. Disease index (DI) data were recorded at maturity, yield was estimated from a central 2- × 1-m sample of each plot.

Propiconazole and thiophanate methyl + thiram significantly reduced disease severity, with corresponding

increases in yield (see table).

Thiophanate methyl decreased disease incidence with no increase in yield. With thiabendazole, iprodione, thiabendazole + maneb, and edifenphos, yield increased but disease did not decrease significantly. □

Effect of N and K on rice sheath rot (ShR) and crop yield

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We applied 5 levels of K, 1 level of P, and 2 levels of N in a 15-m² plot for a field trial. Incidence of ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gam. was recorded 1 wk before harvest.

Disease incidence (DI) decreased with increased K (see table). Increasing the N level but with no change in P increased DI. □

Rice ShR and yield in Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment (kg/ha) of			Disease incidence (%)	Decrease (%) over control	Grain yield (kg/plot)
N	P	K			
75	62.5	0	45	–	4.0
75	62.5	50	37	17	4.3
75	62.5	100	26	43	4.6
75	62.5	150	17	62	4.8
75	62.5	200	11	75	5.1
125	62.5	0	50	–	4.4
125	62.5	50	42	16	4.8
125	62.5	100	31	38	4.9
125	62.5	150	21	57	5.4
125	62.5	200	16	68	5.7
LSD (P = 0.01)			3		ns

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Insect management

Using mixtures of buprofezin and cypermethrin or deltamethrin for green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro virus (RTV) control

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Buprofezin, a slow-acting insectistatic compound, has high activity against *Nephotettix virescens* nymphs and is 50 to 100 times more effective than conventional insecticides. It is slow acting. It does not kill adult insects; only nymphs die during molting to the next instar. Deltamethrin and cypermethrin, which are pyrethroids, have quick knockdown effect on GLH adults.

Table 1. Field evaluation of buprofezin and deltamethrin for GLH control.^a IRRI, 1986.

Insecticide ^b	Rate (g ai/ha)	GLH (no./10 hills) ^c at 1 DAT				Hills (no.) showing RTV symptoms at 65 DT
		1st spraying		2d spraying		
		Adult	Nymph	Adult	Nymph	
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	50 + 6	1.3 ab	0.8 a	1.8 a	39.8 ab	7.5 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	75 + 6	1.3 ab	0.5 a	1.8 a	29.5 ab	6.9 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	6 + 13	1.0 ab	1.0 a	1.8 a	12.0 ab	5.0 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	25 + 13	1.0 ab	0.5 a	0.3 a	15.0 ab	5.4 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	75 + 13	1.0 ab	2.0 a	3.5 ab	8.5 a	5.0 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP	50	2.8 ab	28.8 b	3.3 ab	18.3 ab	10.8 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP	75	3.8 b	24.5 ab	7.0 bc	73.5 bc	13.0 b
Deltamethrin 2.5 EC	13	0.5 a	0.3 a	2.0 a	11.3 ab	6.0 bc
BPMC 50 EC	750	3.0 ab	15.5 ab	4.3 ab	34.8 ab	12.5 b
Untreated		4.0 b	20.0 ab	11.3 c	109.5 c	21.8 a

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b Insecticides were applied at 20, 35, 50, and 65 DT. Spray volume was 300-500 liters/ha. ^c Av of 4 replications. DAT = days after treatment.